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Chief Editor

Dr. T. Pradeep Kumar

Co-Editor

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A Study of Environmental Attitude of Pupil-teachers in Relation to their Gender, Stream and Location

Dr. Ritu Bala Aggarwal*

ABSTRACT

The teacher-training programme should be designed to equip trainee teachers for how to inculcate attitude through different subjects and this requires that pupil-teachers should have positive attitude towards environment to manifest responsible environmental behaviour among students. It is felt necessary to investigate whether the teachers, who are disseminating the knowledge, are equipped with positive attitude towards environment so that they may shape up the behaviour of their students. Therefore, if we wish to achieve the aim of inculcating the positive attitude towards environment among students and save our environment from further degrading, we have to study the environmental attitude of the pupil-teachers of teacher training colleges. Present study endeavours to study the environmental attitude of pupil-teachers in relation to their gender, stream and location. A sample consisting of 600 teachers was selected from randomly pooled five teacher training colleges affiliated to Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra. The results clearly indicate that the female pupil-teachers have more level of environmental attitude than their counterpart male pupil-teachers do. There is significant difference between the environmental attitude of pupil-teachers belonging to arts and science streams. Also, the rural pupil-teachers have more environmental attitude than their counterpart urban pupil-teachers.

Keywords: Environmental Attitude, Attitude, Pupil-teachers, Environment, Teacher training colleges.

INTRODUCTION

National Policy on Education, 1986 (India) and NCFSE (2000) highlight the need for including Environmental concerns at all the levels of schoolings. The Honourable Supreme Court of India has endorsed a model syllabus (2004) prepared by the NCERT for introducing environmental studies as a compulsory subject. With all efforts from agencies responsible for determining quality education, school teachers have the major duty to instill attitude among students through the subjects they are teaching in school so that students could behave sensibly towards the environment and contribute towards the up-gradation of the environment. For this noble task, it is necessary that teacher-training programme should be designed to equip trainee teachers for how to inculcate attitude through different subjects and this requires that pupil-teachers should have positive attitude towards environment to manifest responsible environmental behaviour among students. It is felt necessary to investigate whether the teachers, who are disseminating the knowledge, are equipped with positive attitude towards environment so that they may shape up the behaviour of their students. Hence, it is pertinent to study the environmental attitude of the students of teacher training programme.

Positive attitude towards environment is convincing teachers at all levels and stages that it is an integral part of their duty to organize environment related effective curricular and co-curricular activities. The study of Shahnawaj (1990) revealed that 95% teachers and 94% students possessed positive environmental attitudes. Praharaji (1991) found that there was moderate correlation between environmental knowledge and environmental attitude. Sabhlok (1995) found that urban teachers differed significantly from rural and tribal teachers on their awareness of environmental problems. No difference was observed between rural teachers and the tribal teachers. Dinakara (2000) reported significant difference between urban and rural school teachers in environmental awareness. Deb and Srivastava (2007) found that there is a significant positive relationship between environmental

responsibilities and environmental values. The study conducted by Kumar and Patil (2007) has revealed that students with environmental education background has better environmental attitude and there is no significant difference between male and female students in their attitude towards environmental pollution and related issues. Sengupta *et al.* (2009) found that sighted and visually impaired students belonging to secondary stage of education in West Bengal do not differ with respect to pro-environmental behaviour and gender. Sudeshna Lahiri (2011) has found low correlation between environmental attitude and responsible environmental behaviour of pupil-teachers while there is a significant correlation between responsible environmental behaviour and scientific attitude. Ashraf (2012) has found that students of private schools of urban areas of Bhopal have better environmental attitude than their counterpart students of government schools of rural area. Shrivastava (2013) has found that girls have more environmental awareness than the boys do.

Therefore, if we wish to achieve the aim of inculcating the positive attitude towards environment among students and save our environment from further degrading, we have to study the environmental attitude of the pupil-teachers of teacher training colleges. Present study endeavours to study the environmental attitude of pupil-teachers in relation to their gender, stream and location.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To find out the level of environmental attitude of pupil-teachers.
2. To compare the environmental attitude of male and female pupil-teacher.
3. To compare the environmental attitude of pupil-teachers belonging to arts and science streams.
4. To compare the environmental attitude of pupil-teachers belonging to rural and urban area.

HYPOTHESES

1. There is no significant difference between the environmental attitude of male and female pupil teachers.
2. There is no significant difference between the environmental attitude of pupil-teachers belonging to arts and science streams.
3. There is no significant difference between the environmental attitude of pupil-teachers belonging to rural and urban area.

Delimitations

1. The study is confined to the Ambala District of the state of Haryana.
2. The study is confined to the pupil-teachers pursuing B.Ed. degree.

Method

Considering the nature of the problem under investigation descriptive survey method of research was used.

Sampling

The population of the study was pupil-teachers pursuing B.Ed. degree in college of education of Ambala. A sample consisting of 600 teachers was selected from randomly pooled five teacher training colleges affiliated to Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra.

Table-1: Distribution of Sample

	Urban		Rural	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
Arts	75	75	75	75
Science	75	75	75	75

Environment Attitude Scale by N.N. Shrivastava and Shashi Dubey has been used for data collection.

DATA COLLECTION

The researcher personally visited the colleges and collected data from the pupil-teachers. The pupil-teachers were given Environment Attitude Scale and they were asked to fill up the same.

ANALYSIS AND STATISTICAL TREATMENT OF DATA

T-test was used for the analysis of data. The results are presented in the following tables:

Table-2: Summary Level of Environmental Attitude of Pupil-Teachers

Range of Scores	Level	Frequency	Percentage
37 and less	Most Unfavourable	4	0.67
38-44	Unfavourable	91	15.17
45-51	Intermediary	95	15.83
52-58	Favourable	240	40.00
59 and Above	Most Favourable	170	28.33
Total		600	

Mean = 54.69; Median = 55; Mode = 54; Variance = 70.05; S.D. = 8.37; Range = 42 (78-36)

Figure-1: Level of Environmental Attitude of Pupil-Teachers

Table-3: Environmental Attitude in relation to Gender

Stream	M	S.D.	N	df	t	sig
Science	57.94	7.66	300	258	3.21	0.01
Arts	51.45	7.77	300			

Table value: $.05 t = 1.97$ and $.01 t = 2.59$

Table-4: Environmental Attitude in relation to Stream of Study

Location	M	S.D.	N	df	t	sig
Rural	57.62	7.38	300	258	3.02	0.01
Urban	51.77	8.27	300			

Table value: $.05t = 1.97$ and $.01t = 2.59$

Table-5: Environmental Attitude in relation to Location

Location	M	S.D.	N	df	t	sig
Rural	57.62	7.38	300	258	3.02	0.01
Urban	51.77	8.27	300			

Table value: $.05t = 1.97$ and $.01t = 2.59$

FINDINGS

1. It is clear from the Table-3 that the mean environmental attitude of female pupil-teachers came out to be 58.23 as compared to 51.17 of male pupil-teachers. The t-value testing the significance of mean differences came out to be 3.38 that is significant at 0.01 level of confidence.
2. It is evident from the Table-4 that the mean environmental attitude of science pupil-teachers came out to be 57.94 as compared to 51.45 of arts pupil-teachers. The t-value testing the significance of mean differences came out to be 3.21 that is significant at 0.01 level of confidence.
3. It may be observed from the Table-5 that the environmental attitude of rural pupil-teachers came out to be 57.62 as compared to 51.77 of urban pupil-teachers. The t-value testing the significance of mean differences came out to be 3.02 that is significant at 0.01 level of confidence.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on findings following conclusions were drawn:

1. There is significant difference between the environmental attitude of male and female pupil teachers. The female pupil-teachers have more environmental attitude than their counterpart male pupil-teachers.
2. There is significant difference between the environmental attitude of pupil-teachers belonging to arts and science streams. The science stream pupil-teachers have more environmental attitude than their counterpart arts stream pupil-teachers.
3. There is significant difference between the environmental attitude of pupil-teachers belonging to rural and urban area. The rural pupil-teachers have more environmental attitude than their counterpart urban pupil-teachers.

SUGGESTIONS.

In the light of the findings of the present study, following are some suggestions that can be used by Government, teacher-training institution, teacher-educators and policy-makers to improve the level of environmental attitude of pupil-teachers:

1. Curriculum of teacher-education programme should be reformed (both theoretical and practical) making pupil teachers as well as teacher educators understand the aims, objectives methods, scope and importance of environmental values and giving birth to inculcate values to protect and save our environment for tomorrow.

2. The teacher-training programme should stress upon developing scientific attitude among pupil teachers irrespective of their discipline.
3. The community outreach programme should be organized and pupil-teachers should be made to survey the rural regions where they can observe how people are thriving on 'nature' and to organize awareness programmes in villages, towns, slums and industrial areas.
4. The experiences of in-service pupil teachers should be shared and invited to train pre-service pupil teachers convincing them that it is an integral part of their duty to organize environment related effective curricular and co-curricular activities.
5. Teaching strategies should be evolved through researches in the area of eco-psychology to bridge the gap between man and the nature and developing among pupil-teachers the general awareness of environmental degradation and problems at local, national and international level.
6. Teacher training institutions should join hands with policy makers to arm prospective teachers with methods and strategies so that they can efficiently teach in schools how renewable and non-renewable resources could be used and protected to preserve, conserve and sustain for future generations.
7. Pupil-teachers should be trained to use co-scholastic activities in other subjects as a medium of teaching education for bringing positive, eco-friendly environmental attitude.

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